

Tillage implements for soil incorporation of carbofuran granules in rainfed wetland fields

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Carbofuran as a systemic granular insecticide is readily translocated in rice plants when taken up by the root system. Broadcasting carbofuran granules into the paddy water after transplanting is inefficient because the high water pH causes chemical breakdown and rains wash granules out of the field.

Placing the granules in the plant's root zone by tillage (soil incorporation) is more efficient. But in rainfed wetland environments, the paddy fields dry out during the dry season. When land that has been prepared is flooded, it is difficult to produce a good loose soil structure to facilitate soil incorporation. Furthermore, the delay in land preparation after the onset of rains allows weeds to flourish, hindering tillage in the fallow fields.

We tested five tillage implements used by farmers in the Manaoag Cropping Systems research site, Pangasinan, to determine which of them most effectively incorporated insecticide in the soil, as indicated by whorl maggot and early stem borer control. Animal-drawn implements were used in the normal preparation of four farmers' fields for the single transplanted rainfed crop. The fields were plowed once and harrowed twice before the final harrowing. The implements used for the final harrowing, during which 1 kg a.i. carbofuran/ha was soil incorporated, were:

1. an 8-hp IRRI-designed power tiller,
2. a wooden paddle wheel rotary harrow (*padulang*),
3. a metal comb harrow (*suyod*),
4. a bamboo flat-frame harrow with teeth composed of short stout nodal branches (*kalmot*),
5. a wooden flat-frame harrow with iron teeth (*kalmot*), and
6. a wooden flat-frame harrow with teeth up for a leveling operation.

All implements except the power tiller were carabao-drawn.

The treatments were compared with a paddy-water broadcast application 5 days after transplanting (DT) and an untreated check. For stem borer and leaf folder control, all plots including the check were protected during the later growth stages with sprays of 1 kg a.i. endosulfan/ha at 34, 45, and 55 DT (see table). For rice bug control, the plots were treated with three sprays of 1 kg a.i. gamma BHC/ha at weekly intervals from the post-flowering to the hard dough stage.

All tillage implements provided equally adequate soil incorporation of carbofuran granules to control whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina* and stem borer deadhearts caused by *Scirpophaga incertulas*. They also resulted in yields significantly higher than those of the paddy water application treatment and the untreated check.

Comparison of tillage implements for soil incorporation of carbofuran granules in a single crop of transplanted IR36. Manaoag, Pangasinan, Philippines. 1979. ^{a/}				
Tillage implement ^{b/}	Carbofuran (kg a.i./ha)	Whorl maggot grade 30 DT ^{c/}	Stem borer deadhearts (%) 45 DT	Yield (t/ha)
Power tiller	1	1a	0.5a	5.4a
Paddle wheel harrow	1	1a	0.4a	5.2a
Comb tooth harrow	1	1a	0.3a	5.3a
Bamboo box harrow	1	1a	0.5a	5.4a
Wooden box harrow teeth down	1	1a	0.4a	5.2a
Wooden box harrow teeth up	1	4b	2.8b	4.7b
None ^{d/}	0	8c	6.2c	4.2c
^{a/} Av of 4 fields/replication. DT = days after transplanting. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P < 0.01).				
^{b/} One pass after granules broadcast.				
^{c/} 1-9 scale: 1 = 0-1% leaves damaged, 3 = 2-33% damaged leaves, 5 = 34-50% damaged leaves, 7 = > 50% damaged leaves, but no broken leaves, 9 = > 50% damaged leaves with broken leaves.				
^{d/} Granules broadcast into the paddy water 5 DT.				